

1. Research Questions

- RQ1:** Comparison of GaWPs between a Mobilise-D population and healthy controls
- RQ2:** Association between a GaWP and a clinical measurement at a single timepoint
- RQ3:** Prognostic value: Longitudinal association between a GaWP and a clinical measurement or outcome over time
- RQ4:** Use of GaWPs as endpoints in controlled interventional studies

2. General Eligibility Criteria

Criterion	Include	Exclude
2.1 Pub. Type	Peer-reviewed literature, Grey literature, Conference papers, PhD theses	Master's theses Protocols (will be indexed for RQ4) Clinical trial registration (indexed for RQ4) Papers with no original results Reviews & Meta-analyses
2.2 Study Design	RQ1 Case-control, cross sectional study, cross-sectional analysis of a longitudinal study,	Animal studies Case studies Case series
	RQ2 Cross sectional study, cross-sectional analysis of a longitudinal (cohort) study,	Systematic or non-systematic reviews Protocols (will be indexed for RQ4)
	RQ3 Longitudinal (cohort) study or longitudinal analysis of the control arm of an interventional study	
	RQ4 Randomized or non-randomized controlled trials, including comparator trials and crossover design trials	RQ4: Uncontrolled interventional trials
2.3 Technology	Basically any (sensors, stopwatch, speed gates, instrumented walkways, video, optometric systems, pedometers, etc.) Specific clinical tests regardless of technology use (see below)	Self-reported daily activity/steps
2.4 Setting	Any (home, clinical, lab-based, inpatient, outpatient, indoor, outdoor)	NA
2.5 Minimum Dataset	>= 10 patients per study arm included in the final analysis	<10 patients per arm in any relevant analysis

3. Population Eligibility Criteria

Include	Exclude
-Confirmed diagnosis of Multiple Sclerosis by a professional physician based on the relevant diagnostic criteria at the time of the study's publication -Any age range and disease severity level will be included -Any sub-type of MS (RR, PP, SP, PR)	Animal studies Clinically isolated syndrome (CIS), Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder (NMOSD), Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG), or Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM)

- If the population is mixed, the study must conduct a sub-analysis of one of our populations to be included.

4. Gait and Walking Parameters

Temporal Parameters

Cadence (mean, variability)
Step time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Stride time (mean, variability)
Stance time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Swing time (mean, variability, asymmetry)
Single support time (mean, variability, asym.)
Double support time (mean, variability)

Spatiotemporal Parameters

Gait speed (mean, variability)
Stride speed (mean, variability)

Volume of Walking

Daily Walking time
Daily Step count
Number, length, duration of walking bouts

Spatial Parameters

Step length (mean, variability, asym.)
Stride length (mean, variability)
Step width (mean, variability)

5. Eligible Walking Conditions

5.1 - Included walking conditions:

- Gait analysis or measurement of any included gait parameter (real world, lab, or clinic)
- Single-task, double-task, straight, curvilinear, with or without turns, with or without obstacle avoidance
- Some clinical tests, even if no technology was used:
 - 4, 5, 10, 30, 50, etc. meter walk (or other short distance) – INCLUDE as gait speed
 - Timed 25 Foot Walk (T25FW) - INCLUDE as gait speed
 - 2 Minute Walk Test – INCLUDE as gait speed

5.2 - Conditionally Included:

- Timed Up & Go: ONLY INCLUDE instrumented TUG w/ GaWPs measured during walk
- Treadmill Walking:
 - Fixed-Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed
 - Self-Adjusting Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP
- 3/4/6/12-Minute WT, 400m WT, (or other long walking tests):
 - Non-Instrumented Test: EXCLUDE
 - Instrumented test: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed

5.3 - Excluded Walking Conditions (If GaWPs are measured ONLY in these conditions)

- Walking in time to cues (e.g., beats, music, beeping, mental singing, etc.)
- Walking during gait training (e.g., during a VR or auditory stimulation intervention)
- If a condition you encounter is unclear, raise a question to the group

5.4 - Excluded Walking Motions (If GaWPs are measured ONLY during these motions)

- Turning, gait initiation, gait termination, stair climbing, response to sudden stimulus or push, or other specific subsets of walking tasks
- Tandem walking, wide step walking, or other *intentional* non-natural walking
Purposefully altering gait (e.g., instructions to concentrate on lifting toes)
- If a condition you encounter is unclear, raise a question to the group

Note: Papers studying excluded conditions and motions could still be included if normal gait was analyzed at baseline (RQ1/2) or as an outcome after intervention (RQ4)

6. RQ 1 Eligibility Criteria

Included Methods

- GaWPs meeting all other eligibility criteria are compared between a target population and a healthy population

7. RQ 2 Eligibility Criteria

Included Methods

- Establish the relationship between an included measure and a GaWP at a single timepoint
- Correlations, trends over stratified analyses, odds ratios, and other association measures are included

Included Measures

	Category	A - All disease areas	B – MS-specific Instruments		
1	Disease Severity & Symptoms	CGI (clinician global improvement), PGI (patient global improvement)	EDSS, FSS, PDDS, SNRS, Number of relapses, EDMUS-GS	1	
2	Functional Status/ADL	Barthel Index, Nottingham EADL, IADL, LLFDI FIM	Schwab & England, MSIS-29, MSFC, MSRS-S, GNDS, Neuro rating scale from Scripps	2	
3	HRQoL	EQ-5D (5L or 3L), EQ-VAS, SF-36 (RAND) SF-12, SF-MCS, SF-PCS, HUI3, LSQ	MSQoL-54, MSQLI, FAMS PRIMUS, MusiQoL, PROMIS, Neuro-QoL	3	
4	Mental Health (Depression, Anxiety, Apathy)	HADS, Beck, CES-D, GDS, SDS/Zung, PHQ (2, 8, or 9), MHI, GHQ	MS Depression rating scale NeuroQOL Depression	4	
5	Cognition	MMSE, MoCA, SDMT PASAT, CANTAB, CAMCOG-R,	ACE-R, PDQ, BICAMS, MSNQ, MACFIMS, BRNB	5	
6	Falls	FES-I, Incidence of falls		6	
7	Physical Function	Walking or Functional Assessments	6MWT, TUG, STS, SPPB	MSWS-12	7
8		Motor Function & Balance	ABC, Berg Balance, FAB, BESTest, mini-BESTest, Ambulation Index (AI)	9-HPT Disease Step (DS)	8
9		Physical Activity	IPAQ, PASE, GLTEQ		9
10		Strength	Knee flexion (hamstring), Knee extension (Quadriceps), Leg press, Grip		10
11		Fatigue	FIS, mFIS, FSS, FACIT, U-FIS	MS-FSS	11
12	Physiological Measures	NA	Number/volume of lesions Brain volume, BWCS, BLCS, IVIS	12	

Further information on included measures are included in the protocol supplemental materials

9. RQ 4 Eligibility Criteria

Included Methods

- Controlled studies, including comparator and crossover studies
- A GaWP is used as a primary, secondary, or exploratory endpoint

Excluded Methods

- Uncontrolled Studies
- Studies where an included GaWP is not measured as an outcome
- No new data available (protocols and registrations will be indexed but not analyzed)

8. RQ 3 Eligibility Criteria

8.1 - Included Methods

- Univariate models, longitudinal associations, prediction models, multivariate analyses, and machine learning models that assess the relationship between a GaWP at baseline and an outcome at follow-up.
- Include retrospective or prospective analyses

8.2 - Excluded Methods

- Models based on cross-sectional data (these belong to RQ2)
- Prediction models where gait speed/walking volume is the outcome

8.3 - General Outcomes: All disease areas

- Disease/Disability Status or Progression
- Health-Related Quality of Life
- Mortality
- Healthcare Utilization (e.g., hospitalizations, readmissions, home care, costs, invasive procedures, etc.)
- Physical Function (e.g., exercise capacity, motor function, balance, strength)
- Functional Status (e.g., activities of daily living)
- Fatigue
- Cognition
- Mental Health (e.g., depression, anxiety, apathy)
- Falls
- Life Space
- Residential Status
- Use of Mobility Aids

8.4 - MS-Specific Outcomes

- Relapses
- Lesions & Brain Volume

Further information on included outcomes are included in the protocol supplemental materials